

An Analysis of EFL Instructors' Use of Information and Communication Technologies in English Preparatory Classes After Covid-19 Pandemic*

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ABSTRACT

In today's evolving information society, integrating information and communication technologies (ICT) into English language teaching is crucial for instructors. This study examines EFL instructors' use of ICT in English preparatory classes using a descriptive, qualitative method, by which phenomenological interviews provided deeper insights into quantitative findings, using semi-structured interview techniques. Most instructors perceived ICT as beneficial, enhancing content, saving time, enabling diverse material design, and boosting student motivation and participation. The study discussed perceived barriers and enablers of ICT use, aligning with existing literature. Implications were provided for researchers, practitioners, and higher education institutions to support full ICT integration.

Keyword: Information and communication technologies, language teaching, technology

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Covid-19 Sonrası Öğretim Elemanlarının İngilizce Hazırlık Sınıflarında Bilgi ve İletişim Teknolojileri Kullanmaları Üzerine Bir Analiz*

ÖZET

Günümüzün hızla gelişen bilgi toplumunda, bilgi ve iletişim teknolojilerinin (BİT) İngilizce öğretimine entegrasyonunu, öğretim elemanları için kritik hale gelmiştir. Bu çalışma, İngilizce hazırlık sınıflarında İngilizce öğretim elemanlarının BİT kullanımını, betimsel ve nitel bir yöntemle incelemektedir. Fenomenolojik görüşmeler, yarı yapılandırılmış görüşme formu kullanılarak nicel bulgulara daha derin içgörüler sağlamıştır. Çoğu öğretim elemanı, BİT'in faydalı olduğunu, içeriği zenginleştirdiğini, zaman tasarrufu sağladığını, çeşitli materyal tasarımı imkânı sunduğunu ve öğrenci motivasyonunu ile katılımını artırdığını düşündüğü tespit edilmiştir. Öğretim elemanları tarafından algılanan BİT kullanımını mümkün kılan ve engelleyen durumlar ilgili literatürde tartışılmıştır. Çalışmanın sonunda, BİT'in tam entegrasyonu için araştırmacılar, uygulayıcılar ve yükseköğretim kurumları için bulgulara dayalı öneriler sunulmuştur.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Bilgi ve iletişim teknolojileri, dil öğretimi, teknoloji entegrasyonu, öğretim elemanları.

Introduction

In recent years, and particularly after the global shift prompted by the COVID-19 pandemic, the use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) has become increasingly embedded in nearly all areas of daily life. However, despite this growing integration, many argue that ICT is still not utilized at a satisfactory level in the education sector. When compared to other sectors such as business, banking, and healthcare, a significant gap remains between the potential and actual use of ICT in education (Buabeng-Andoh, 2012; Chisăliță & Cretu, 2015). In response, numerous countries have increased their investment in ICT to build teaching and learning environments that align with the demands of the digital age. Both developed and developing nations aim to integrate technology into their education systems to meet strategic objectives, including narrowing educational disparities, transforming traditional education models, enhancing global competitiveness, equipping students with 21st-century skills, and ensuring equal learning opportunities for all. The COVID-19 outbreak in 2020 served as a crucial turning point, offering a real-world test of these ongoing ICT investments in education.

Nevertheless, as of 2025, it has become increasingly evident that the widespread availability of ICT in education does not automatically lead to its effective or transformative use in pedagogical practice (Nugroho & Zulfiani, 2021; Hidayati et al., 2021). While the COVID-19 pandemic acted as a catalyst for rapid digitalization, especially in remote learning environments, much of the implementation has remained limited to basic functional applications (Maree & Vos, 2021). Many educators continue to rely on ICT tools for administrative tasks or content delivery, rather than using them to support active, student-centered, and inquiry-based learning (Sinuraya et al., 2024; Aristeidou et al., 2020; Nurita et al., 2023). This is largely due to a lack of continuous professional development, insufficient digital pedagogy training, and the absence of structured models that integrate technology meaningfully with curriculum objectives (Zakiyuddin et al., 2022; Sulawanti et al., 2021).

Moreover, although national and institutional policies often emphasize digital transformation and 21st-century skills, the translation of these goals into everyday classroom practices remains inconsistent. Infrastructural challenges, unequal access to reliable internet and devices, and socioeconomic disparities continue to restrict opportunities for equitable participation in digital learning (Fegely et al., 2020). These limitations have become more apparent with the increasing integration of artificial intelligence in

education. While AI-driven tools offer personalized learning experiences and automation, they also bring new concerns related to ethics, data privacy, educational equity, and the shifting roles of teachers and institutions (Hutapea et al., 2020; Baldock & Murphrey, 2020).

In this context, the gap between the envisioned benefits of ICT integration and the realities faced by educators and learners persists. Closing this gap requires not only investment in technological infrastructure, but also a systemic commitment to pedagogical innovation, digital inclusion, and long-term support for teachers as active agents in the transformation of education (Safitri, 2023; Opticia et al., 2022). After the coronavirus (COVID-19) has been classified as a global pandemic, many countries have taken strict measures to prevent its rapid spread such as lockdowns, regulations for social distancing, school closures, etc.; however, some countries have preferred not to take any precautions and allowed the pandemic to proceed in its normal course. These complete lockdowns have introduced us new ways of doing what we normally do, they have changed our lives in a way that things would not be as they were in the past. Many have started to work from home, organizations have provided flexible working hours, or the governments have closed institutions or organizations where the people could be infected with the virus. Schools, on the other hand, were closed for the rest of the term almost all over the world, some universities announced they will continue online education in the coming semester, and whether the rest will be open in the new semester is still in question. It is reported that more than 1.5 billion learners of all ages more than in 190 countries throughout the world are affected because of the school and university closures due to the COVID-19 (UNESCO, 2020; UNICEF, 2020). The school closures have expanded the learning inequalities and the students were the most affected as not all had the same opportunities with the ones living in the city centers or had the necessary tools to carry out their academic studies.

The pandemic introduced us the new ways of teaching and learning, which raises the importance of ICT use by everyone enrolled in education sector. In general, ICT can be defined as a set of technologies that allow the information to be collected and processed, stored and automatically transferred to another location or accessed remotely with electronic and / or optical technologies when necessary (Ceyhun & Çağlayan, 1997). The need to integrate ICT into education in the information age is a must as the internet has been growing largely and becoming a part and parcel of the working and educational life. Many developments, improvement and integration plans have been in action at national and international level in

computerization, teacher education, student's access to ICT tools, updating curricula, etc. to keep up with the pace of the rapid development of ICT. Turkey set out to enhance this with the development of Fatih Project in 2010 and added Education Information Network (EBA) to its resources. Fatih Project in education was initiated for the effective use of information technology tools in courses to address more senses in the learning-teaching process in order to provide equal opportunities in education and training and to improve the technology in our schools. Five principles lie at the fundamentals of Fatih Project: accessibility, productivity, equality, measurability and quality (Fatih Projesi, 2020).

Learning management systems (LMS), open learning resources, social networks, lecture videos, synchronous - asynchronous lectures and mass open online lectures have been started to be used widely for educational purposes in some higher education institutions.

As a result, although the necessity of the ICT integration is increasingly understood in today's information society, there are uncertainties and contradictory research findings about what is meant by ICT use, how to measure it, and which conditions can be associated with ICT use and results in educational settings. Therefore, more studies are needed to examine the conditions associated with ICT use, the results of ICT use and ICT use in a comprehensive and in-depth manner.

Changes in expectations related to quality in education, changing social needs, changes in information and communication technologies and the effects of these technologies on teaching and learning, changes in student profile, changing paradigms in teaching and learning form the basis of professional development needs of teachers. Teachers, who form the human resources of the education system, have important roles and responsibilities in realizing the teaching profession and in training individuals in line with changing social needs. The use of information and communication technologies in educational environments and the diversification and change of learning resources change both the roles of teachers in the teaching-learning process and the methods of performing professional development activities. From this point of view, the related literature on ICT and the use of ICT in education was reviewed and presented below.

In their studies, in which they conducted in-depth, semi-structured interviews with 16 teachers in the province of Badajoz, Malagón and Pérez (2017) found out that the majority of teachers think that ICT presupposes an incredible development for instruction in common, but none of them think that computers in part demonstrate an insurgency within

the field of education as it used to be, and they do not favor excessive use of computers in language classrooms, as in traditional teaching as they hinder their advancement and typical dynamics. In another study conducted with 100 preservice teachers to determine their perceptions on children's reading skills in EFL via ICT, Thuy (2020) found out that preservice teachers have positive perceptions and are willing to use ICT in their teaching of reading in EFL to pupils. In their study conducted with the English instructors for non-English Study Program students at IAIN Curup, Apriani & Hidayah (2019) stated that the instructors mainly use only three types of ICT in their teaching; speaker, educational games and website resources since they are easy and cheaper to reach although there are many other types of ICT available.

Muslem and Juliana (2017) stated in their study conducted with 26 English language teachers to determine their perceptions and challenges to use ICT in ELT classroom that English language teachers think ICT is very helpful in teaching but they face obstacles such as limited time, insufficient equipment and weak internet connections, in addition to the lack of knowledge and experience and lack of ICT education to completely make use of ICT in their teaching. Rodliyah (2018), in their study to investigate the ways the vocational high school English language teachers integrate ICT into their teaching and the obstacles and benefits they face, suggested that all the teachers integrate ICT into their teaching moderately due to their internal motivation, interest and their perception on its benefits. In another study carried out with 400 EFL teachers in China, Li & Walsh (2011) found out that although most of the schools provide an adequate classroom setting and most teachers have enough computer skills, teachers' use of ICT is mostly limited to PowerPoint presentations of pictures, grammar and sentence structures. They also determined that the obstacles that prevent the teachers from using ICT effectively in their classrooms are lack of adequate training, lack of time, lack of technical support when needed, lack of training and the need for a more integrated approach to ICT integration.

In their study, Ertmer, Ottenbreit-Leftwich and York, (2006) stated that enablers just like barriers can be categorized into intrinsic or extrinsic, and access to ICT equipment, software, technical support, internet can be considered among extrinsic enablers and personal beliefs, competence can be considered among intrinsic enablers. Hammond, et al. (2009) also stated that having access to ICT and technical support is a key element in terms of effective use of ICT in the classroom by teachers. In addition, Bingimlas (2009) suggested in their study that sustained technical support should be provided to the teachers. Li and Walsh (2011) found out that teachers' access to

computers and the internet in their offices and classrooms increase their motivation to use ICT in language teaching. Buabeng-Andoh (2012) also stated that the fact that the teachers integrate and use ICT effectively in their classrooms mainly depends on the presence and accessibility of these tools.

Bingimlas (2009) stated that the main barriers in the use of ICT are lack of confidence, lack of competence, and lack of access to resources even though teachers had a strong desire for to integrate ICT into their teaching. In their study conducted in Vietnam, Peeraer and Petegem (2010) also stated that the use ICT in education is unrealized mostly because of the ICT skills of the teachers and computer confidence although access to computers and ICT tools is not a barrier for the teachers. Pham, Tan and Lee (2018) stated that the lack of supporting IT personnel and lack of qualified personnel are big barriers for the teachers to integrate ICT in their teaching. In the study by Baek (2008) on identifying the factors hindering teachers' use of computer and video games in the classrooms, it was determined that using ICT tools and games in the classroom is hindered because of lack of supporting and reference materials. Dang, Nicholas and Lewis (2012) stated that the main barriers to using ICT are lack of training on ICT, lack of support to use ICT in teaching. On the other hand, Tearle (2003) suggested that well-motivated and caring staff would work tirelessly for quality, and they would understand the necessity to re-evaluate and adapt their workflow on a regular basis in a variety of ways, including thorough evaluation of ICT use.

Tondeur et al. (2007) stated in their study conducted with 570 teachers that there is a gap between the proposed and implemented curriculum for ICT and lack of communication between the school principals and teachers in terms of implementing ICT in schools. Dang et al. (2012) also determined in their study carried out with 222 academic staff in Vietnam that there are barriers in the integration of ICT into teaching both at institutional and teacher level, among which are lack of guidelines, training and support for ICT use in teaching, and limited resources. Another study carried out in Vietnam by Dinh (2009) with 12 teachers established that support is an important element for the teachers to use ICT in their teaching as well as trainings on teaching English with ICT. In their study carried out with 55 teachers, Mushayikwa and Lubben (2009) stated that ICT use triggers the teachers' self-directed professional development.

Ertmer (2006) points out in their study with 25 winners of statewide technology teacher awards that it is necessary to pay more attention to intrinsic factors like beliefs, attitudes, and confidence during undergraduate education and more interaction of pre-service teachers with exemplary teachers will increase

their use of ICT in the future. Muslem and Juliana (2017) stated in their study with 26 English teachers at senior state high schools in Banda Aceh that age of teachers has no effect on the implementation of ICT in language learning. In their study Goktas et al. (2009) carried out on the main barriers and possible enablers for the integration of ICT in preservice teacher education programs, it was stated that universities can designate particular units or staff to provide technical support, offer assistance the public to use ICT tools and materials in educating, and offer assistance to decrease the educators' workload. Sang et al. (2018) also found out in their study carried out with 340 teachers to analyze the actual and preferred perceptions of 21st century learning competencies that their perceptions of meaningful use of ICT have significant, positive correlations with collaborative learning, critical thinking, self-directed learning, creative learning, and problem solving. They also stated that the teachers using ICT in their teaching perceive less barriers in integrating and using ICT in their teaching.

Teachers generally view ICT as a significant advancement for education, particularly in language teaching, but many believe it does not revolutionize the field and prefer moderate use to avoid disrupting traditional classroom dynamics. While preservice teachers show enthusiasm for using ICT to teach reading in EFL, its application is often limited to basic tools like PowerPoint, speakers, educational games, and websites due to ease and cost. Barriers to effective ICT integration include insufficient training, time constraints, inadequate equipment, weak internet, lack of technical support, and teachers' low confidence or skills, despite access to tools not always being an issue. Support, such as technical assistance and training, is critical for encouraging ICT use, which can foster self-directed professional development and enhance skills like collaboration and critical thinking, though gaps between curriculum plans and actual implementation persist.

Statement of the Problem

It is a fact that ICT creates new roles and practices for EFL instructors. The contemporary teaching approaches to language teaching places importance in student-centered approaches, new roles for students and teachers. With the integration of technology, teachers have become facilitators that has less control in transferring the knowledge, which makes students active in learning and that transforms the classrooms into an environment in which the information is structured by the student.

Considering that the ICT integration process in education is largely influenced by the social, cultural and organizational context (Fullan, 2007; Karaca, Can, & Yildirim, 2013), the ICT use of the instructors who

teach English as a second language defined as *lingua franca* and work in universities which are increasingly adopting the sustainable development movement worldwide (Waas, Verbruggen, & Wright, 2010), doing research and education at a high level is discussed in this study. Since it is not yet known to what extent EFL instructors use ICT in university preparatory classes, this study aims to address EFL instructors' experience of using ICT in their teaching: the benefits of using ICT to facilitate teaching, the barriers to using ICT to facilitate teaching and the factors that determine the use of ICT to facilitate teaching. Although there are many efforts to increase the use of ICT in education in Turkey, research on ICT, CALL and MALL can be said to be limited, however research on other topics such as attitudes of teachers and students and the effect of ICT on language learning has been conducted in the primary, secondary and high school level. Universities are the gates that creates, experiments and serves the science. Therefore, it is thought that conducting a study on the university level on the use of ICT by the EFL instructors who are the ones creating, experimenting and serving the science will fill the gap in the current literature.

Study Purpose and Research Questions

This study aims to investigate EFL instructors' use of information and communication technologies (ICT) in preparatory classes to enhance English language teaching quality, a critical factor since the emergence of Computer Assisted Language Learning in the 1960s. ICT integration, increasingly vital in Turkey since the 2010s, enables interaction beyond classrooms and enriches learning through online and authentic materials. The Turkish Statistical Institute (2019) reported a rise in household computer use from 43.2% in 2010 to 59.6% in 2018 and internet access from 41.6% to 88.3% by 2019. Initiatives like MoNE's FATİH project (2010) and CoHE's Digital Transformation project, implemented in eight universities, promote ICT infrastructure and digital skills training. The study examined concepts influencing the ICT experiences of the instructors working at universities, and assessed reported ICT use, facilitators, and barriers. It seeks to recommend solutions for enhancing ICT integration in preparatory classes and contribute to the literature with insights specific to Turkey.

In this context, the study seeks answers to the research questions below:

1. *What do EFL instructors perceive as enabling them to use ICT?*
2. *What do EFL instructors perceive as barriers to using ICT in teaching?*

The rapid technological advancements of the past two decades have revolutionized education, making the

integration of information and communication technologies (ICT) in EFL teaching critically important for enhancing student engagement, motivation, and learning retention. This study is vital as it addresses the urgent need to understand EFL instructors' ICT use, a relatively underexplored area despite extensive research on other ICT aspects. By examining how internet, computers, and mobile devices facilitate learner-centered education, collaborative learning, and anytime access to information, the study underscores the necessity of technology in modern EFL classrooms. The emergence of University 4.0, with its focus on blended learning and career-ready graduates, further highlights the significance of adapting teaching to digital contexts. This research is crucial for revealing current ICT practices among EFL instructors, identifying integration challenges, and proposing solutions for effective technology planning, thus providing a foundational contribution to future studies and the optimization of teaching-learning processes in higher education.

Research Design

In this research, a descriptive research process was adopted to examine EFL instructors' use of information and communication technologies (ICT) in their prep classes. In the qualitative dimension a phenomenological process was carried out in order to examine and explain the data presented by the EFL instructors teaching in the preparatory classes regarding the quantitative research questions in a more detailed way. In this context, qualitative data were collected using the semi-structured interview technique.

Participants

After reaching a decision to use a semi-structured interview technique in collecting the qualitative data, an interview protocol was developed by the researcher based on the one of Gamlo (2014). The purpose of conducting interviews was to further examine and describe the quantitative results obtained during the research process. 37 out of 175 participants of the questionnaire were volunteered to participate in the interviews but the convenience sampling method was used to determine the interview sampling to represent the target population. Due to the limitations in terms of time, money and workforce, the convenience sampling method brings speed and practicality to the research as the sample is selected from easily accessible and applicable units (Karasar, 2013). So, 17 out of 37 volunteers to participate in the interviews were selected.

According to Mertens (2019), the researcher is the data collection tool during the interviews. The researcher decides which questions to be asked, what to be observed and what to be noted down. In this

context, firstly the quantitative results of the research were determined, and preliminary questions were prepared to determine the phenomenological perceptions of the participants regarding these results. Three questions from Gamlo's (2014) interview protocol was directly used in our study and some other were modified to reflect the cultural aspects as both studies are parallel in terms of determining the similar aspects of ICT use. The researcher made a pre-interview with an EFL instructor in order to determine whether the questions he prepared in this direction were expressed clearly in the pilot study. The pre-interview was conducted individually and the interview lasted 15 minutes. After the interview was completed, the answers given by the instructor to the interview questions were analyzed and transcribed. This instructor was later excluded from the scope of the research. In order to determine the content validity of the interview protocol to be used in the study, the preliminary questions prepared were presented to the expert opinion and were used in the final form in line with the feedback received. There is a total of 9 questions in the interview protocol and the response time is approximately 15 minutes. The form is suitable to be evaluated as an interview or can be filled in writing.

The interviews were conducted online due to the COVID-19 pandemic in 2021. The interviewees were first contacted through email or phone and were asked for an appointment. They were also informed about the software to be used for the interviews. The interviews were conducted with Skype, a free Microsoft software used in many interviews, and the interviews were recorded with a sound recording software comes with Windows.

Findings

This chapter of the study presents the qualitative data findings obtained from the interviews. As previously mentioned, the interviews were conducted with 17 volunteer participants (n=17, 10 females, 7 males) through a semi-structured interview protocol. During the interviews, the teachers were asked 9 questions aiming to reveal their ICT experience in teaching and the following themes:

Figure 1. The Coding Scheme of the Themes related to ICT Use of The Instructors

The interviews were listened and transcribed into digital environment and read carefully more than once to set a coding scheme about the themes. The participants of the interviews were coded as T1, T2, T3,.....T17.

The Instructors and Their Teaching

The first question of the interview examines the instructors, their teaching experience and the challenging and unchallenging aspects of teaching EFL. The longest professional seniority is 22 years and the arithmetic mean of the participants (n=17) is 10,76 in terms of professional seniority. Only two of the participants stated that they worked at other institutions for one or two years before they started working at the university they currently work for. Only one of the participants has a BA from the department of translation and interpretation, 6 of them from department of English language and literature, 10 of them from the department of English language teaching. It can be said that all of the instructors are qualified enough to teach EFL since they (n=15) have Mas and the others (n=2) have PhD. Accordingly, it can be said that most of instructors got the adequate knowledge about how to teach using new approaches or technologies as it can be understood from the statement of T2 that they had difficulty in the transition of being a translator and interpreter or a teacher of English:

"I should confess that teaching has always sounded to be an inferior occupation to me, so I avoided being a teacher as I had the license to work as a translator and interpreter as a relatively more prestigious and posh job. (I am never after more money) The biggest challenge I have ever faced in teaching is the gap between the main cognitive functions involved in translating/interpreting and teaching. These two are so distinct areas that I often felt shocked and lost, checking twice if I am dealing with two different dimensions of one same field."

It was determined that all of the participants use ICT in their prep classes whether compulsory or not. Yet, some of the instructors, whether young or old, prefer their own teaching methods, which makes it harder for them to integrate ICT in their prep classes although some of the courses require them to use ICT like the courses which aim teaching listening and speaking skills. It is surprising to find out that T9 who have been teaching EFL for 22 years seemed very interested in using ICT especially in material design classes while some of the younger or less experienced ones call using ICT "their nightmare."

"I mainly integrate it in material development courses. I guide my students to search and use, adapt and implement digital materials for various ages of learners. We have the technical equipment in classrooms. Today, no lessons can motivate and engage learners if there is no integration of ICT."

Even though some of the instructors were very interested and overeager to use ICT tools in their

teaching, the settings of their classrooms did not allow them to completely integrate ICT in their teaching since they only had OHPs without internet connection, so it pushed them to use just ppts or some other slide software when they started working. But with the very first step of digital transformation of the universities in Turkey, they had the internet in their faculties and only with an OHP, they were able to include ICT tools in their teaching. It is a well-known fact that every university in Turkey used to provide a laptop or PC to each of its instructors until 2016, after when some of the universities have started to provide only PCs.

One of the instructors (T13) stated that even though they had a smartboard in the classrooms spared for their department, it is of no use since no other instructors even slightly try to use it.

"Well, we have a smartboard in one of our classrooms and it is used as a speaking club but as none of other professors uses it but me, it is generally jammed or broken. Sometimes I manage to open it, but I have never been able to connect it to internet."

Among the instructors with MA on ELT, T17 has a strong belief that ICT facilitates the teaching and learning, increases the motivation of the students and attracts their attention more than he has expected. It can be said that this is a substantial aspect of ICT in terms of teaching English to Turkish students who have lower motivation to learn even if it is considered to be an important skill to get a job in the future.

"Using mobile apps and games during the classes help the students stay focused on the subject and thus their learning becomes permanent and supporting them with games and some other visuals help them recall what they have learnt during the class. This particularly applies when it comes to teaching vocabulary."

Almost all of the instructors interviewed share the opinion that ICT is valuable and important in teaching even though majority of them do not integrate it to their classes completely. For example, T9 states:

"I want the students to write down what is on the board, but instead, they always ask my permission to take a picture of it before I clean the board. At first, I used to tell to write down but in time I come to the understanding that even though I tell them to write down, some take pictures secretly and share them in their WhatsApp groups. And now I warn them to take pictures before I clean the board."

The statement above shows that even though some instructors do not want to use ICT tools in their teaching, it is inevitable for them to get use to ICT as their students are born to it and it has a significant part in their lives. It can be said that the younger the instructors, the more they are likely to use and accept ICT in their classes as they themselves use those

tools more and effectively in their daily lives compared to elder ones.

The Source of Motivation of the Instructors

The instructors were asked whether using ICT in their classes has an impact on their teaching compared to without using it. The underlying cause of this question is to reveal the source of their motivation. Although many of the interviewees responded in detail about the question, others' responses were brief. Many of them stated that teaching with ICT has a great impact on both their students and classes as it helps draw the attention of the students easily and helps them stay focused on the subject. The instructors stated that:

"What we are dealing with is the generation Z, so students having smart phones connected to the internet by themselves all the time, it is very easy for them to be distracted. Here comes the technology. Whenever I use the smart board or overhead projector to carry out an activity, they suddenly become interested and are very curious about what the next activity is going to be. With a classroom full of students focused on what is going on, it becomes more and more enjoyable even for me." (T11)

"Computers, smartboards and other technological tools make the classes more interactive. The more interactive a class is, the more efficient fun it becomes. I can say it is one of the best motives for the students." (T2)

One of the participants stressed that using ICT can appeal to multiple senses, which contribute to the permanence of learning. As each student in a classroom setting is unique and has different learning domains, learning styles and interests, ICT can be a very effective tool in appealing all those domains, attracting their interest and designing proper lessons for different learning styles. It was also stated that using ICT in terms of time management is another important aspect of advantages of technology.

"Time management becomes easier when you use technology as it allows you to design your lessons effectively and even in crowded classrooms, almost all students get to participate. It also allows you to address different senses of the students and trigger their learning, so their learning becomes permanent." (T1)

"Sure, there are. Among many, the most important ones are being time-saving both for students and teachers and enabling to use a wide range of materials very easily and quickly." (T5)

It was also stated during the interviews that even if some instructors do not want or choose to use ICT in their teaching, their managements make it compulsory as some of their sources they use in the classroom requires some technological tools to be used. Even if they do not have an option, it is understood that they are also satisfied with the results.

"Here comes the tricky part! Yes, I use ICT in my teaching because I have to use it to a certain extent. My school makes it compulsory because of some activities and means of teaching. Though such requirements are not at a super advanced level,

they look scary at first because learning to use a technological tool/software is more difficult than anything else for me, at least at a perceptive level! But after a few hours' awkwardness, I feel more relaxed to use ICT every time." (T16)

One of the instructors stated that using technology intensely would make the classes dull in time as of traditional teaching methods. The main reason why s/he uses ICT in their classes is to make sure s/he has a diversity of teaching techniques to maintain participation and make the classes fun.

"I believe it's not teaching with technology that I am trying to do in my classes. I am just including it sometimes. Not all the time. I am paying specific attention to not to overdo it lest it gets traditional and boring for my students. (However, I do have a google classroom for each course and we are using it actively.) Using technology has its advantages I agree. However, the reason why I am including it in my classes is not because the literature suggests so: it is because my students are in generation z, and they have fun, and they are participating more when technology is included." (T3)

Source of Satisfaction of the Instructors

As a result of the qualitative analysis, it was determined that most of the instructors expressed their source of satisfaction as the impact of ICT use on students' learning. The main indicator of this is the increase of the students' participation in the classes and as a result, improved test scores, language use skills.

"Using ICT tools also increase the students' motivation, so they take more active part in the teaching process. The way you design the classes help the students maintain their own learning. It is very obvious that it also helps them become more successful in their test scores." (T7)

"Teaching with technology helps one become more flexible and thus confident. It also makes you a modern, effective and impressive trainer. And this has a substantial effect on your students, as well. ...it becomes clear that even the shy ones start to talk or ask questions during the lesson. In the long run, you can your students' language skills have increased, which is a satisfaction for a teacher to do what he is supposed to." (T12)

"When you do not use technology, you close your doors and the doors for students to the outside world and pretend you are guiding them to work in real environments. But with technology included in the lessons, you open the doors to the real world and be able to show them real life situations where they can actually use their language skills." (T6)

Some of the instructors were pleased with the outcomes of being an instructor, which are working with the young and having a good career in higher education which is considered as a prestigious profession in the society.

"I decided to choose a financially secure career and interact with young people as it would be exciting to experience hierarchical difference with individuals who are almost of my age. I particularly chose to teach in tertiary education due to the smaller age difference, which would give me less of the feeling or being called as a "teacher". (T15)

"I can mention one big but maybe insensible thing: I like being called "hocam" by my students. A less frequent outcome is the occasional achievements of students which come as a result of

my efforts within and outside the class. It makes me feel that I make a difference to others' lives." (T11)

"I love working with younger generation as they have different characteristics and most of the time, they are open-minded and ready for novelties." (T16)

It was also determined that working as an instructor in a higher education institution may have an impact on being also a researcher. Doing postgraduate research and contributing to the relevant literature is another source of motivation for the instructors. T4 with B.A. stated that:

"I have always wanted to be a teacher of English language. While taking my B.A courses, I have realized that in order to improve the quality of 'teaching English' in our country, there needs to be improvements in how teachers are trained. That is why I have been working on teacher education in my studies, which in return makes me happy to contribute, even if it is just a little bit, to the literature."

Source of Dissatisfaction of the Instructors

The instructors' major source of dissatisfaction related to the use of ICT was questioned during the interviews. Different explanations were put forward for their source of dissatisfaction. Among them, the most striking was the rigid syllabus of the books they use in their prep classes. Recently published textbooks include online assessment and allow students to use digital materials but the textbooks published years ago do not have the tools of the digital age, so they make it difficult for the instructors to use ICT tools in their teaching. T10 stated that:

"Since it is difficult to buy newly published textbooks, which are very expensive considering the economic condition of Turkey, for our students from families with poor economic conditions, we take into consideration this. Of course, we want the best for our students, but the economic conditions sometimes do not allow us for the best. So, we use some cheaper textbooks which can be affordable for all our students, and that makes it difficult to use technology in the lessons as there left not enough time to catch the syllabus of these textbooks."

Some of the instructors' stated that designing lessons with ICT takes more time as they are not familiar with it. The main reason behind this can be that the more the instructors have professional seniority, the more they tend to think they are better at designing lessons on their own traditional way.

"Turkish students are very shy when it comes to speaking English. Their high school teaching experience may have an impact on this. I design my lessons for my students to be able to participate without forcing them. Of course, I am not the best teacher, but I believe my experience taught me a lot to contribute to the learning of my students" (T13)

Even though working with the young has some advantages in terms of using technology in the class, some of the instructors stated that this can be tricky sometimes as their students are not quite motivated to participate even if they prepare games or videos to make the classes fun.

"The target audience of course. This is somehow dependent on your students' openness and willingness. If they are not in the mood, like after a difficult exam or a tiring day, you can do your best to use what you have prepared, but no chance!" (T16)

One of the instructors stated that psychological barriers are another source of dissatisfaction for their use of ICT. S/he feels insecure about if something goes wrong with the activity carrying on.

"Psychological barriers! They hold me from being easy with those "monsters". It is because of the errors or irregularities popping up at any time. They are really discouraging and stay forever in my subconscious mind." (T12)

Another stated that this is mostly based on the nature of the crowd you are dealing with. Even though it may seem to be fun for the students, it does not have the same impact on each of them and different classes.

"Well, it depends on the nature of the class and ICT tool. For example, once when I was doing Kaboots in my writing classes, the students had the utmost fun in one class but in another class the students had no fun at all. I immediately stopped using it with that class and tried to find out the one they would like more." (T3)

Another instructor indicated that even if s/he wants to use ICT, the lack of support and motivation discourage them to integrate it with their classes. This is mostly the case with the Turkish students and the management of the school you work with.

"Sometimes I feel lack of enough support from management and lack of enthusiasm from the students' side. Those things discourage me but still I try to use it." (T9)

One of the instructors emphasized the burden of being a teacher. Coming from another department apart from ELT requires teachers to close the pedagogical gap as they do not get.

"The second biggest con of teaching English, among others, is the realization that you have to educate, bring up, bear and rear, train and everything your students to teach! It is like being a mom, far beyond what I was supposing before starting to teach! It requires you to be a true sufferer rather than being a cool performer of many other jobs. It was a cause of frustration for me." (T2)

Instructors' ICT Use and Its Value

As a result of the qualitative data analysis, it was determined that most of the instructors consider using ICT tools in their teaching as an effective method in terms of reaching the goals they set at the beginning of the academic year. According to some of the instructors, it was seen as very powerful tool to contribute to their students learning. The results of the analysis also showed that most of the instructors use ICT tools to some extent. This includes the use of OHPs, computers, smartboards, internet, email, blogs, educational websites, student information system and moodle.

Using ICT in the classes has a positive effect both on the instructors and students. In addition to its contribution to improving students' learning, it also helps the instructors to benefit from using it like enriching the contents, saving time, designing materials and appropriate syllabus, increasing students' attention and motivation, classes to become more interesting for students, and increasing students' participation.

"Using ICT made an invaluable contribution to my classes. My classes have not been tedious but like the rainbow. Each student can find something appealing to them, so they learn better now." (T17)

"Changing my attitude towards technology increased the attendance and participating of my students to my lessons. I used to be traditional teacher using direct instruction and OHP and some slides, but I realized that this took the students' eye off the ball, and they started to be disappearing from my classes. So, I dig into how to improve my teaching with new teaching methods and came up with the idea of using internet more in my lessons. Now I feel that they are really into my lessons." (T1)

"For example, I use both the digital and paper versions of the books that we use in courses. I reflect the digital book on board and take notes on it beforehand. In this way I think I'm able to connect with students who have different types of learning styles." (T5)

Some of the instructors stated that using ICT helps them save time in terms of preparing materials and using those in their classes.

"There is an app called draw and tell, if the subject of the day is relevant, I encourage my students in the classroom to draw something related to the topic and ask them to talk about their drawings. Podcasts are also a good way to help my students improve their listening skills, so I look for the related podcast and assign it to the students to listen to it after the class. Sometimes it's a good way to save the day and do on what's next." (T4)

In addition to time saving aspects of ICT, T3 stated that using appropriate websites or apps is also a financially economic and environmentally friendly way in teaching.

"Canva is really useful when we finish exploiting a reading text and they need to create poster. It is economical (the students do not have to buy any material), eco-friendly (we do not print anything), and timesaving (the students are familiar with it and can prepare it outside the class and share it on our google classroom) We have online exhibitions and comment on them together on Google classrooms. All tools are beneficial when they are used effectively."

In terms of preparing materials, T11 expressed how ICT can be effective in terms of preparing different and appealing materials for their classes even though it is time consuming for them.

"In preparing my teaching through ICT, I use google keep taking notes instantly when I surf the web and come across something noteworthy and related to the next subject. I used to use ppts but they have been extensively used in education and whenever a student sees a ppt slide, they lose their

attention and sometimes you can see them sleeping, so instead of ppt's, I use Prez!, which is similar but a lot fun for the students to see some different animations (well, if you are not familiar with it, it can take a lot of time to prepare). I use comics, memes and gifs in my slides and prepare them myself on a website for free."

Another value ICT adds to the lessons is the way it increases the motivation and attention of the students according to some of the instructors.

"At the start of the term, I prepare two or three Kaboot games. When we play it in the class, the students love it. After playing it, I deliberately ask them 'Did you like it? Do you want to play again?', and they wholeheartedly say 'YES!' and then I say okay then it's your turn. 'If you like it that much, why don't you prepare one and we play it here together?' It becomes kind of an assignment for them. I deliberately use the word assignment because it makes the negative connotation of it go away. Thus, next time I assign them something they would know that it might be fun for them. Well, in the next class, everyone's Kaboot game is ready, and we play them when we want to play." (T7)

"The key is in not to make it something traditional then even the most creative thing can be traditional, losing the novelty in it, and boring for them. And the most important issue is modelling. If the students are not familiar with the tool, they will feel reluctant in participating. So, firstly, I show them the example, they lead them through the preparation of it step-by-step. Then, I ask them to prepare one for us. Thus, we increase in-class participation and eagerness." (T15)

It was seen that using ICT in the teaching-learning process can help the instructors to make their classes more appealing and interesting for their students. The more the classes are interesting for them, the more eager they will be to construct their learning.

"The students always come to your class in a happy mood, having questions in mind like what fun activity are we going to do today. When they learn a tool in my class, I see them using it in a different class and get positive feedback, which make my classes more attractive to them." (T14)

"I can only say that it is tiresome at some level to prepare all those materials to meet the different interest of the students; however, at the end of the day, I am content with what I am doing." (T9)

Results and Discussion

Having access to technical support can be considered as one of the barriers in terms of using ICT. Hence not all the instructors are familiar with newly developed web tools, they sometimes have difficulty in using them. In their study, Ertmer, Ottenbreit-Leftwich and York, (2006) stated that enablers just like barriers can be categorized into intrinsic or extrinsic, and access to ICT equipment, software, technical support, internet can be considered among extrinsic enablers and personal beliefs, competence can be considered among intrinsic enablers. They also stated that like barriers, intrinsic enablers are of importance for the teachers to use ICT tools compared to extrinsic ones. Hammond, et al. (2009) also stated that having access to ICT and technical support is a key element in terms of effective use of ICT in the

classroom by teachers. In addition, Bingimlas (2009) suggested in their study that sustained technical support should be provided to the teachers.

Quantitative findings of our study showed that there is no significant difference in the attitude sub-dimension while there is a significant difference in the use sub-dimension in terms of having a computer and projector in the classroom and having a set of computers variables. This can be interpreted that having access to ICT tools is an enabler in using ICT in classes. Majority of the instructors believed that not having a single or set of computers is a big restriction in terms of using ICT in their teaching. In the interviews, one of the teachers believed that having a computer without internet connection can also be big restriction as today's coursebook are supported with online materials.

A few instructors consider the support from the management or the university they work for as an enabler to using ICT. Goktas et al. (2009) stated that universities can designate particular units or staff to provide technical support, offer assistance the public to use ICT tools and materials in educating, and offer assistance to decrease the educators' workload.

Inadequate ICT infrastructure was also mentioned by one of the instructors. It can be said that most of the instructors have computers at home or in their offices and have access to the internet yet few of them have computers in the classrooms. Some of the instructors stated that their department provide them music players and laptops to the classroom. Some of them stated that they have to bring their own devices to carry out particularly the listening classes. Li and Walsh (2011) found out that teachers' access to computers and the internet in their offices and classrooms increase their motivation to use ICT in language teaching. Buabeng-Andoh (2012) also stated that the fact that the teachers integrate and use ICT effectively in their classrooms mainly depends on the presence and accessibility of these tools.

Teacher's perceptions of meaningful use of ICT have significant, positive correlations with collaborative learning, critical thinking, self-directed learning, creative learning, and problem solving. They also stated that the teachers using ICT in their teaching perceive less barriers in integrating and using ICT in their teaching (Sang, Liang, Chai, Dong, & Tsai, 2018). Tondeur et al. (2007) stated that there is a gap between the proposed and implemented curriculum for ICT and lack of communication between the school principals and teachers in terms of implementing ICT in schools. It was stated that the teachers have positive attitude in terms of integrating ICT into their teaching practices and the schools are support the teachers in their use of ICT in their teaching and learning (Sahay & Dawson, 2019).

Dang et al. (2012) determined that there are barriers in the integration of ICT into teaching both at institutional and teacher level, among which are lack of guidelines, training and support for ICT use in teaching, and limited resources. Another study carried out in Vietnam by Dinh (2009) with 12 teachers established that support is an important element for the teachers to use ICT in their teaching as well as trainings on teaching English with ICT. Bingimlas (2009) stated that the main barriers in the use of ICT are lack of confidence, lack of competence, and lack of access to resources even though teachers had a strong desire for to integrate ICT into their teaching. In the study by Baek (2008) on identifying the factors hindering teachers' use of computer and video games in the classrooms, it was determined that using ICT tools and games in the classroom is hindered because of lack of supporting and reference materials. Dang, Nicholas and Lewis (2012) stated that the main barriers to using ICT are lack of training on ICT, lack of support to use ICT in teaching.

Survey data of the present study revealed that the personal factors in terms of using ICT is a barrier for the instructors. Even though the majority of the instructors believe in the value of ICT, the psychological barriers to using ICT hinder them to use these tools. Lack of confidence and lack of competence are two mostly stated barriers to using ICT in the related literature. Ertmer (2006) points out in their study with 25 winners of statewide technology teacher awards that it is necessary to pay more attention to intrinsic factors like beliefs, attitudes, and confidence during undergraduate education and more interaction of pre-service teachers with exemplary teachers will increase their use of ICT in the future. In their study carried out with 55 teachers, Mushayikwa and Lubben (2009) stated that ICT use triggers the teachers' self-directed professional development. In their study conducted in Vietnam, Peeraer and Petegem (2010) also stated that the use of ICT in education is unrealized mostly because of the ICT skills of the teachers and computer confidence although access to computers and ICT tools is not a barrier for the teachers. However, it can be said that preservice teachers have positive perceptions and are willing to use ICT in their teaching of reading in EFL to pupils (Thuy, 2020).

One of the instructors used "monster" as a metaphor to define using ICT. This is mainly because of the lack of technical support when needed and not having any training related to ICT tools. English language teachers think ICT is very helpful in teaching, but they face obstacles such as limited time, insufficient equipment and weak internet connections, in addition to the lack of knowledge and experience and lack of ICT education to completely make use of ICT in their teaching (Muslem & Juliana, 2017). Pham, Tan and

Lee (2018) stated that this is because of the lack of supporting IT personnel and lack of qualified personnel. Some of the instructors stated that even though they did ICT classes, it was of no use for them since they were not able to conduct what they had learnt. In the study by Baek (2008) on identifying the factors hindering teachers' use of computer and video games in the classrooms, it was determined that using ICT tools and games in the classroom is hindered because of lack of supporting and reference materials. On the other hand, Rodliyah (2018) suggested that the teachers integrate ICT into their teaching moderately due to their internal motivation, interest and their perception on its benefits.

It has become apparent in the interviews that many of the universities do not support their staff in improving themselves in ICT. Only one of the instructors stated that he had a two-day training related to ICT within the university he worked. Dang, Nicholas and Lewis (2012) stated that the main barriers to using ICT are lack of training on ICT, lack of support to use ICT in teaching. The instructors mainly use only certain types of ICT tools in their teaching; speaker, educational games and website resources since they are easy and cheaper to reach although there are many other types of ICT available (Apriani & Hidayah, 2019). It was also stated that although most of the schools provide an adequate classroom setting and most teachers have enough computer skills, teachers' use of ICT is mostly limited to PowerPoint presentations of pictures, grammar and sentence structures (Li & Walsh, 2011). It was also determined that the obstacles that prevent the teachers from using ICT effectively in their classrooms are lack of adequate training, lack of time, lack of technical support when needed, lack of training and the need for a more integrated approach to ICT integration.

On the other hand, Tearle (2003) suggested that well-motivated and caring staff would work tirelessly for quality, and they would understand the necessity to re-evaluate and adapt their workflow on a regular basis in a variety of ways, including thorough evaluation of ICT use. Geldenhuys and Oosthuizen (2015) stated in their study that motivation of the staff, time, accessibility and financial issues are big barriers for the teachers to fulfill their professional developments. On the other hand, Tearle (2003) suggested that well-motivated and caring staff would work tirelessly for quality, and they would understand the necessity to re-evaluate and adapt their workflow on a regular basis in a variety of ways, including thorough evaluation of ICT use.

Enablers just like barriers can be categorized into intrinsic or extrinsic, and access to ICT equipment, software, technical support, internet can be considered among extrinsic enablers and personal

beliefs, competence can be considered among intrinsic enablers (Ertmer, Ottenbreit-Leftwich, & York, 2006). Access to ICT is another barrier for the instructors to teach with ICT tools. Most of the classrooms are equipped with OHPs only and many of them do not run as expected, which makes it difficult for the instructors to present what they have prepared. A limited number of classrooms in most of the universities have smartboards with internet connection. One of the instructors stated in the interviews that they have only two classrooms out of ten with smartboards. Since today's coursebooks come with online learning management systems (LMS), it is of higher importance to have access to computers and internet. Geldenhuis and Oosthuizen (2015) stated in their study that motivation of the staff, time, accessibility and financial issues are big barriers for the teachers to fulfill their professional developments.

Hammond, et al. (2009) also stated that having access to ICT and technical support is a key element in terms of effective use of ICT in the classroom by teachers. In addition, Bingimlas (2009) suggested in their study that sustained technical support should be provided to the teachers. Li and Walsh (2011) found out that teachers' access to computers and the internet in their offices and classrooms increase their motivation to use ICT in language teaching. Buabeng-Andoh (2012) also stated that the fact that the teachers integrate and use ICT effectively in their classrooms mainly depends on the presence and accessibility of these tools.

The findings obtained from the interviews indicate that younger instructors tend to use ICT more in their teaching compared to the senior instructors, this is because of the younger instructors' interest to learn and integrate ICT into their teaching. It also became clear that having support and technical support increase the motivation of the instructors to integrate ICT more into their teaching. Although using ICT enables them to be more flexible, it is timesaving for both the instructors and the students, and it enables them to use wide range of materials easily, they cannot make use of it because of lack of access, lack of support, lack of adequate training, lack of self-confidence. It has also been determined within the research that most of the instructors prefer using traditional teaching methods even if they have the necessary ICT tools present in their classrooms. They do not use Web 2.0 tools other than PowerPoint presentations and student information system. However, it has been determined that few of the instructors use common Web 2.0 tools.

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